

Proceedings of the Network Institute Academy Assistants program 2018/2019

Editors

Victor de Boer
Antske Fokkens
Christine Moser
Ivar Vermeulen

Preface

This volume contains the proceedings of the 2018/2019 edition of the Academy Assistant program organized by the Network Institute of Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (<http://networkinstitute.org/research/academy-assistants/>). With this program the Network Institute aims to interest bright young master students for conducting scientific research and pursuing an academic career. The program brings together scientists from different disciplines; every project combines methods & themes from informatics, social sciences and/or humanities. For each project, two student research assistants with different research backgrounds work together. The projects result in papers and/or research proposals. The program started in 2010 with 4 projects funded by the KNAW.

For the 2018/2019 edition, seven projects were selected to receive funding based on a review of submitted proposals by an independent committee. Each of these projects was then executed by two Academy Assistants during a 10-month period. The selected projects show a broad range of interdisciplinary research and a diverse range of topics.

In addition to papers and/or follow-up research proposals, the projects were asked to submit final papers describing the outcomes of the research projects. These papers are collected in these proceedings after having undergone a light reviewing process by the coordinators of the program. All papers are co-authored by the respective research assistants (as first and second author respectively), the supervisors and other contributors. They reflect the broad spectrum of interdisciplinary work associated with the networked world.

We would like to thank the proposal review committee for assisting in the selection of the projects. We especially extend a special thank you to Lisa Markslag and Marco Otte for their role in the Network Institute and this program.

We hope these proceedings will provide you with new inspirations for your research and opportunities for new and exiting collaborations.

Sincerely,

Victor de Boer, Antske Fokkens, Christine Moser and Ivar Vermeulen

Amsterdam, 27 August 2020

Table of contents

Francois Meyer; Yvette Oortwijn; Pia Somerauer; Jelke Bloem; Ariana Betti; Antske Fokkens. The semantics of meaning: distributional approaches for studying philosophical text

Yanniek van der Schans; David Ruhe; Wido van Peursen; Sandjai Bhulai. Clustering Biblical Texts Using Recurrent Neural Networks

Lisa Vasileva; Edoardo Guerriero; Isa Maks; Kasper Welbers. Building task-specific stance identification models: an evaluation of the active learning approach

Babette Claassen; Jeroen Borst; Ingrid Vermeulen; Victor de Boer; Chris Dijkshoorn. Linked Art Provenance

Ilze Amanda Auzina; Jenia Kim; Evert Haasdijk; Frank van Harmelen; Piek Vossen. Automated Due Diligence: Building Knowledge Graphs from News